

THE BEHAVIOUR OF COLUMNS FOR THE DESIGN OF PULTRUDED FRAMES: ECCENTRICALLY LOADED TESTS

N.D. Brown¹, D. Anderson², and J.T. Mottram²

¹*W.S. Atkins, (formerly²), UK*

²*School of Engineering, University of Warwick, Coventry, CV4 7AL, UK*

SUMMARY

The experimental results from 10 full-size tests designed to investigate the behaviour of eccentrically loaded columns of pultruded profile are presented herein. The tests were carried out on 203x203x9.53 mm wide flange profiles at a single column height of 4.8m. The choice and magnitude of the moment gradient types adopted during the test program are presented, together with details concerning the design and operation of a purpose built test rig. Reported in the paper are the salient results for load-deflection characteristics, loads levels when the deflection reached height/100, ultimate loads, and the mode of failure. The results provide new information that can be used to prepare guidance for code writers and designers.

KEYWORDS: Pultruded profiles, column behaviour, testing, moment gradients.

INTRODUCTION

Standard pultruded profiles mimic steel structural members in shape and are naturally used in frame construction [1], where advantages such as corrosion resistance, light-weight and electro-magnetic transparency can be exploited to good effect. For skeletal frame construction, both thin-walled I and wide flange profiles are readily manufactured by the pultrusion process. In steelwork they have as equivalent members universal beams and columns. The pultrusion process, and details on standard structural profiles, can be found in the manufacturers' technical publications (see for example [1]). Standard profiles consist of E-glass reinforcement in a thermoset resin matrix. Typically the Young's modulus of profiles in flexure is 20 to 23 GPa. The tensile strength of the thin-walled panels is > 200 MPa along the profile's length, and about half this stress in the perpendicular directions. Standard structural profiles have been used to construct the 38 m span cable-stayed Fiberline footbridge, in Kolding, Denmark, and many other structures including buildings, platforms and walk-ways.

To improve upon the existing design guidance for pultruded frames [e.g., 1, 2], it is essential to develop our knowledge and understanding of column behaviour both in isolation and when part of a structural frame. Failure of pultruded members is often governed by limiting deflection or by instability because the material has high strength-to-modulus ratios. The eccentrically loaded column tests study a member type where there is a combination of axial

compression and flexural stresses. Consequently, the new results presented here and elsewhere [3-7] are starting to provide the basis on which such guidance can be founded.

A three phase programme of laboratory tests on full-sized columns of pultruded profile has been carried out at Warwick University. The aim of the research was to provide new information needed to understand fundamental behaviour and to refine current design guidance [1, 2]. The principal objectives of the project were:

- 1) To investigate the ultimate behaviour of columns subjected to axial load (test phase I).
- 2) To investigate the ultimate behaviour of columns subjected to axial load combined with end-moment (test phase II).
- 3) To investigate the behaviour of partially restrained columns within beam-to-column assemblies (test phase III).
- 4) To develop design guidance for columns and semi-rigid frames.

In Brown, Mottram and Anderson [3] the minor-axis buckling characteristics of the 12 wide flange sections in phase I have been presented. These centrally loaded column tests contributed further results to the world-wide database of some 100 tests on isolated columns. During this phase of the programme a range of profile sizes and column heights were used. These tests showed that local flange buckling can be the ultimate mode of failure for centrally loaded columns of 3.3 m height, and that this mode can lead to sudden and catastrophic collapse of the column. Furthermore, the results highlighted that previous studies on axially loaded columns are incomplete [4-7], and that further tests and analyses are therefore necessary to fully understand the structural behaviour.

This paper presents results from phase II of the programme, which consisted of 10 isolated column tests subjected to a moment gradient about their major-axis. The pultruded profiles were E-glass fibre reinforced/polyester matrix wide flange profiles of size 203x203x9.53 mm. They were tested at the single column height of 4.8 m. The profiles were from the standard range from Creative Pultrusions Inc., Pa, USA. The tests on eccentrically loaded columns focused on bending about the major-axis, since this simulates a popular form of frame construction. At the time of writing the authors believe the results presented are unique, since no other test programme has departed from the straight-forward use of loading an isolated column centrally [4-7].

The moment gradient adopted in the testing was one of the three eccentric loading types shown in Fig. 1. The eccentricities were in increments of 101.6 mm, being large compared to the 1 mm that was found to be inherent in our centrally loaded tests [3]. A general arrangement of the salient details of the rig is shown in Fig. 2.

The rig not only had to subject a specimen to an axial load up to 180 kN, it also had to be designed to apply a moment gradient. To generate the moment gradient it was necessary for the end fixtures supporting the column to resist a considerable shear force, whilst maintaining the ideal pinned-end conditions. The solution to this constraint on the test rig's design and function is given.

Salient results from the moment gradient tests are given and their relevance to developing refined design guidance is introduced.

Single Curvature

Fig. 1: Eccentric loading types.

Fig. 2: Arrangement of test rig for moment gradient testing (type I loading shown).

DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS

To meet its objectives a crucial aspect of the test programme was the design and construction of a test rig which would enable all three test phases to be completed. A purpose built test rig, capable of applying an axial load of up to 575 kN was therefore needed which would satisfy the following design criteria:

1. Stability of the rig and specimen during the initial setting-up procedure and subsequent loading sequences.
2. The knife edge restraints at either end of the specimen were as far as was practicable free of friction.
3. One end grillage should be free to move in the 'X' direction (see Fig. 2) with the minimum of frictional resistance created through the necessity to provide restraints to prevent any out-of-plane displacements.

The rig was specifically designed to ensure that the direction of deformation and subsequent buckling would take place in a horizontal plane. The fixed and moveable grillages were constructed from steel channel sections bolted together. These were subsequently linked with threaded Lee Mc-Call high tensile steel prestressing tendons (see Fig. 2). To improve the overall stability of the rig four tendons, two on each side at 1100 mm centres and a vertical separation of 640 mm, were incorporated to form the completed loading frame. In the test set-up, the tendons were aligned such that they pulled straight under the application of the axial load.

It can be seen from Fig. 2 that the directional restraints required at each end of the rig were similar. The difference lay in the necessity to allow the moveable grillage a degree of freedom in the 'X' direction. To prevent any movement in the 'Y' direction, vertical rolling restraints were provided to a centrally positioned stabilising arm, in conjunction with ground level guide rollers located either side of the moveable grillage. Full restraint in the 'Z' direction was thought to be of a lower priority, since for movement to occur in this direction, the dead weight of the grillage must first be overcome. However, for consistency a horizontal rolling restraint was applied to the stabilising arm. This has been omitted from Fig. 2 to aid clarity. The fixed grillage was restrained in the 'Z' direction by way of fixity to the laboratory strong floor and fully braced in the other directions. Following completion of the test rig construction, a load test was carried out to assess the force necessary to displace the moveable grillage against the various rollers. This was subsequently found to be 0.4 kN, resulting in a coefficient of static friction of approximately 0.03. This was considered by the authors to be small enough not to significantly influence the test results.

The actual length of a column specimen was 4.5 m. The total length between the simple supports was 4.8 m (see Fig. 2). The presence of the end fixtures, of length 0.3 m, did not effect the deformation characteristics. Problems associated with the overall alignment of the two ends was carefully controlled using standard surveying techniques, whereupon an overall misalignment of < 2 mm was achieved. Inevitably, because of the nature of the loading arrangement, an internal moment within the test rig was generated. The fixed grillage end will have a substantial ability to resist such a moment. However, the same cannot be true for the moveable grillage end, since it is permitted to move in the 'X' direction. To ensure stability under these circumstances a moment resisting connection between the moveable grillage and the stabilising arm was provided and is shown in Fig. 2.

A column specimen was positioned horizontally in the test rig with the ends confined by cleated steel base plates bonded and bolted to the flanges of the pultruded profile. These plates react through knife edge contacts, which were orientated to be perpendicular to the minor-axis through the column specimen. Knife edges were secured to both ends of the test rig and consequently, rotational freedom was only permitted in one direction. End conditions were therefore simple about the major-axis and fixed about the minor-axis. Moreover, the knife edges were considered insufficient to transmit the shear force perpendicularly to their rotation axis. The shear force at the end of the columns was generated to maintain static equilibrium under the moment gradient. Fig. 3 shows a handed pair of cam follower bearing plates that were precision machined to the radius defined by the rotation of the knife edges. The cam fixture was secured to the knife edge base using hardened dowels. This new feature to the test rig was specifically designed to transmit the shear force.

Fig. 3. Knife edge restraint featuring cam follower bearing plates.

INSTRUMENTATION AND TEST PROCEDURE

The instrumentation set-up given below was chosen to capture results at the ends, and at the quarter and centre points along the column's height.

Column ends:

- a) Applied axial load;
- b) axial shortening;
- c) rotation applicable to the column ends.

A 600 kN hydraulic actuator with a PC control system was used to apply the load by way of displacement control. The axial shortening and end rotations about the vertical axis were measured with linear displacement transducers.

Quarter and centre points:

- a) Lateral displacements in the direction of deformation via linear displacement transducers;
- b) cross-sectional rotations via electronic clinometers;
- c) direct surface strain on the flanges and web using 6 mm strain gauges, positioned 25 mm from the edge of each flange outstand and located centrally on the web.

The instrumentation system was continuously monitored through a Solartron SI3535D data logger, and converted into meaningful results when appropriate. Before the commencement of each test, an estimate of the geometrical imperfections of each column member was obtained. Particular emphasis was directed towards lack of straightness and cross-sectional dimensions.

The test procedure was based on incrementing the load or displacement in small steps. The axial load, and thereby the moment, was gradually increased until either the mid- or quarter-point lateral displacement exceeded 48 mm (i.e. a displacement equal to column height/100), or failure occurred. The load or displacement value for the next increment was decided as the results were plotted. This procedure allowed the steps to be reduced as the criterion to terminate the test was approached. The duration of each test was approximately 4 hours.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The moment gradient applied about a column's major-axis induced either single or double curvature bending of the type indicated in Fig. 1. These gradients were dependent upon the eccentricity of the applied load, with respect to the geometrical centre through each column. For the single curvature tests (types I and II), the eccentricities were varied from 101.6 mm to 406.4 mm in increments of 101.6 mm (i.e. 4 inch), whereas, for the double curvature tests two eccentricities were considered, namely 101.6 mm and 203.2 mm.

There is not space to provide a full presentation and analysis of the results; for interested readers such an in-depth consideration of the eccentrically loaded tests will be found elsewhere [8]. In what follows the salient results and principal observations from the 10 column tests will be given. Table 1 presents the type of loading adopted, together with the maximum load, maximum end-moment and the mode of failure.

Table 1: Test Results

Test No.	Loading type	Eccentricity e (mm)	Axial load P (kN)	End-moment Pe (kN.m)	Mode of failure
from [3]		≈ 1	130	0.1	Euler buckling
1	SI ²	101.6	124 ¹	12.6	Large deflection
2	SI	203.2	70 ¹	14.2	Large deflection
3	SI	304.8	48 ¹	14.6	Large deflection
4	SI	406.4	36 ¹	14.7	Large deflection
5	SII ³	101.6	164 ⁴	16.7	Local buckling
6	SII	203.2	114 ⁴	23.2	Local buckling
7	SII	304.8	80 ¹	24.4	Large deflection
8	SII	406.4	63 ¹	25.6	Large deflection
9	D ⁵	101.6	181 ²	18.3	Local buckling
10	D	203.2	137 ²	27.8	Local buckling

Notes:

1. Deflection exceeded 48 mm or height/100 mm.
2. SI is Single curvature type I loading.
3. SII is Single curvature type II loading.
4. Instability failure occurred before deflection attained 48 mm.
5. D is Double curvature loading.

It can be seen from Table 1 that failure was associated with either a deflection limit (of height/100) or local flange buckling. The instability mode of failure was found when the column was subjected to either single curvature type II loading having an eccentricity < 304.8 mm, or to double curvature. Buckling occurred because the combined axial and bending compression stress was sufficient to cause flange instability when the deflection was below 48 mm.

Figs. 4 to 6 give plots of the axial load against lateral deflection characteristics for nine of the columns. The experimental data points are given by the solid diamonds in the figures. In the case of the single curvature columns Nos. 1 to 8 the deflection was measured at the mid-height. Note that for columns 5 to 8, having unequal moment loading (see type II in Fig. 1), this was not the location where the deflection was maximum. The deflection was zero, as required, at the mid-height during the double curvature test No. 10 and therefore the quarter-point deflection is given in Fig. 6. The load-deflection plot for column No. 9, when the eccentricity was 101.6 mm, has been omitted because its deformation shape did not fit the expected behaviour and consequently its results are still under investigation.

Fig. 4: Load against central displacement for single curvature type I loading.

Fig. 5: Load against central displacement for single curvature type II loading.

Fig. 6: Load against displacement when the eccentricity is 203.2 mm and moment gradient changes.

Fig. 6 also gives the response of a 4.8m column with load eccentricity of 203.2 mm and the three types of moment gradient.

The first row in Table 1 gives the results, with ‘zero’ load eccentricity, for a 203x203x9.53 mm profile deforming about the minor-axis. All other boundary conditions were identical to those in the single curvature type I tests (Nos. 1 to 4 in Table 1). When the loading was central [3] the mode of failure was by way of the global Euler buckling. An estimation of the Euler buckling load for instability about the major-axis (which can occur only if there is restraint to buckling about the weaker minor-axis) is given on scaling the 130 kN in Table 1 by the ratio of the major-axis-to-minor-axis second moment of areas (i.e. 4.17/1.33). The axial load with no moment gradient is therefore estimated to be 410 kN. When the eccentricity is 101.6 mm, and higher, the wide flange column deforms as a conventional column-beam [9]. The maximum axial load is lower than the major and minor Euler buckling loads because the lateral deflection due to bending exceeded the criterion of height/100. The higher the eccentricity the lower was the maximum axial load and vice versa for the end-moment.

Lateral deflection occurs from the onset of loading and its value at the mid-height, Δ , is given by

$$\Delta = e \times \left(\sec\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{P}{P_e}}\right) - 1 \right) \quad (1)$$

where e is eccentricity
 P is axial load

P_e is the Euler buckling load (equal to $\frac{\pi^2 EI}{L^2}$), in which EI is the flexural rigidity and

L is the column height.

I is $4.13 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^4$ and the flexural modulus E is 23 GPa (E_L in [3]) for Creative Pultrusions’ standard profile 203x203x9.53 mm. Equ. (1) is known as the secant formula and is valid for slender columns with a symmetric cross-section [9]. The formula does not need to take into account the effect of shear deformation because it can be neglected for a column height > 3 m [3].

Using Equ. (1) the theoretical load against deflection is plotted in Fig. 4 for columns Nos. 1 to 4. Theoretical data points are given by the solid circles. There is a close correlation between the theoretical deflection and what was determined in the test. It is therefore concluded that while the response is governed by flexural deformation, the classical 'steel' thin-walled analysis, as given in [9], is valid. Equations similar to Equ. (1) were also taken from [9] and applied to the other two moment gradient types. The very good correlation between theory and experiment are shown in Fig. 6 for column tests Nos. 6 and 10 when the eccentricity is 203.2 mm. Solid circles are used to give the theoretical data points. The excellent correlation provides further evidence to support the use of classical analysis to calculate column deflections when their deformation is described by beam-column behaviour [9].

Fig. 5 presents the results for the single curvature tests when there was an unequal moment (see Fig. 1). Such a column condition simulates the physical situation of an external column in a single storey frame. At its base we assume the column-to-base is nominally pinned (no moment) while at its top there is, on one side, a beam joined to the column in the major-axis orientation. The beam is connected to the column by way of a web cleated connection [1, 2]. The vertical load component can therefore be modelled by a shear force acting at an eccentricity of 100 mm from the column flange surface. Previous tests on isolated columns do not simulate such a practical situation and therefore the new results are relevant to the preparation of improved design guidance. It is noteworthy that none of the published design guidance, such as given in [1] and [2], consider a column with a moment gradient loading.

CONCLUSIONS

The performance of the test rig was satisfactory when used to generate the moment gradients. Results from the 10 column tests with eccentric axial loading are novel and need to be fully analysed. Load against deflection plots from testing are shown to have characteristics similar to those expected when the column is steel (i.e. classical isotropic slender column theory is acceptable after suitable modification for the 'flexural' modulus). The mode of failure is often excessive deflection and this can be quantified using existing theory. Under specific conditions the moment gradient deformation led to column failure by way of the local flange buckling mode. This mode of failure cannot yet be predicted accurately [see 3], especially when it occurs due to a combination of axial and bending compressive stresses. There is an urgent need for theory that can predict flange buckling resistance under general column loading. The new results provide a basis for refined design guidance provided local buckling is not the failure mode.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge support for the research project from the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC), UK., and for the material contribution from Creative Pultrusions Inc., USA.

REFERENCES

1. Anon. “*EXTREN Design Manual*”, Strongwell, Bristol, VA., 1989.
2. Clarke, J.L., (Ed.), “*Structural Design of Polymeric Composites - EUROCOMP Design Code and Handbook*”, E & FN Spon, London, 1996.
3. Brown, N.D., Mottram, J.T., and Anderson, D., “The Behavior of Columns for the Design of Pultruded Frames: Tests on Isolated Centrally Loaded Columns”, *Proceedings of Second International Conference on Composites in Infrastructure*, 5-7 January 1998, Saadatmanesh, H., and Ehsani, M.R., Eds., Vol. II, pp. 248-260.
4. Scott, D.W., Yoon, S.J., and Zureick, A., “Full Scale Tests on Concentrically Loaded Fibre Reinforced Pultruded Columns,” *Proceedings Materials: Performance and Prevention of Deficiencies and Failures*, Material Engineering Congress, White, T., Ed., ASCE, NY, 1992, pp. 572-576.
5. Barbero, E., and Tomblin, J., “Euler Buckling of Thin-Walled Composite Columns”, *Thin-Walled Structures*, 17, 1993, pp. 237-258.
6. Tomblin, J., and Barbero, E., “Local Buckling Experiments on FRP Columns”, *Thin-Walled Structures*, 18, 1994, pp. 97-116.
7. Zureick, A., and Scott, D., “Short-term Behavior and Design of Fiber-Reinforced Polymeric Slender Members under Axial Compression”, *Journal of Composites for Construction ASCE*, 1 4, 1997, pp. 140-149.
8. Brown, N.D., Mottram, J.T., and Anderson, D., “Experimental Investigation into the Buckling Characteristics of Pultruded Columns - Response under Moment Gradient”, in preparation.
9. Gaylord, E.H., and Gaylord, C.N., “*Design of Steel Structures*”, 2nd Ed., McGraw-Hill, 1972.